

Grazing Banks - the Finnish case Laidunpankki

www.eurafagroforestry.eu/afinet/

The Grazing Bank (Laidunpankki.fi) facilitates contact between land owners and animal owners. Nowadays, not every farm owns animals and not every animal farm has access to sufficient suitable grazing land. In this online tool, it is easy to search for grazing land available for leasing (meadows, fields, forest pastures), or animals (cattle, sheep, horses) if you want to lease your own land for grazing.

In addition, the web service contains information on service providers (fencing, animal transport, animal control, fighting invasive species), as well as other services like shepherd holidays. Practical information on e.g. animals stocking rates, investments costs or agri-environment subsidies is also available.

The advisory organization ProAgria can assist in the management plan of the areas of the agreement. The web service has a national scope. Similar land bank services already exist in some other countries too, either at national, regional or local level, and a similar concept could be applied in more countries. For instance, a grazing bank would be a very interesting tool as forest fires prevention method, contributing to reverse land abandonment and assist new generations to make a living in the countryside.

Links:

Grazing Bank Finland, Laidunpankki:

<https://www.laidunpankki.fi/>

Grazing Bank Galicia, Spain, Banco de terras:

<https://agader.xunta.gal/gl/banco-de-terras>

Finnsheep is a traditional Finnish livestock breed. Photo by Michael den Herder.

Mercedes Rois
Michael den Herder
European Forest Institute